

STUDIES ON GENETIC VARIABILITY, HERITABILITY AND GENETIC ADVANCE IN COTTON (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.)S. N. Devkule¹, S. D. Pathan^{*2}, H. V. Kalpande³, T. R. Ghorpade⁴, S. L. Shinde⁵, P. Ramu⁶, K. Shiva⁷ and S. R. Ithape⁸^{*2,4&6} M.Sc. students, Department of Seed Science and Technology, College of Agriculture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.¹ Assistant Professor, Cotton Research Station, Nanded, Maharashtra, India.³ Head, Department of Seed Science and Technology, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.⁵ Ph.D. students, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.⁷ M.Sc. students, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.⁸ M.Sc. students, Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

The present investigation was attempted to study the evaluation of *hirsutum* cotton genotypes for yield, fibre and seed quality traits through various estimates, as genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, heritability, per cent of mean for genetic advance, genetic variability. The experiment was carried out with 20 cotton genotypes including 17 American cotton genotypes with three checks viz., NH-677, NH-615 and NH-545 in Randomized Block Design with three replications at Cotton Research Station, Nanded during kharif, 2024-25. Genotypes were evaluated and observed at field as well as lab were recorded for twenty different traits comprising yield, fiber and seed quality characters. Twenty characters viz., Days to fifty percent flowering, Plant height, Days to maturity, Number of sympodia per plant, Number of monopodia per plant, Number of bolls per plant, Boll weight, Seed cotton yield per plant, Ginning percentage, Upper Half Mean Length, Micronaire value, Tenacity 3.2 mm, Elongation, Test weight, Germination, Seed Vigour Index- I, Seed Vigour Index - II, Seed dry weight, Seed moisture content, Seed Index were studied. The character viz., number of monopodia per plant and seed cotton yield per plant recorded high phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean was observed for most of the characters viz., number of monopodia per plant, seed cotton yield per plant, boll weight and seed vigour index-II. These characters could well be improved by resorting to simple pureline selection.

Key words: genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, genetic variability, heritability, Genetic advance, pureline selection.

Introduction

The word cotton has been mentioned in the ancient Indian *Vedas* and the existence of cotton thread traced back to the *Rigveda* about 4000 BC. Cotton is grown worldwide for its natural fibre and source of oil, and the cottonseed meal is used as feed for ruminant livestock (Wallace *et al.* 2009). Cotton is an important fiber crop of global importance, which belongs to the genus *Gossypium* and family Malvaceae. It is considered as the “King of Fibre Crops” or “White Gold”. There are four cultivated species of cotton viz., *Gossypium arboreum*, *G. herbaceum*, *G. hirsutum* and *G. barbadense*. The first two species are diploid (2n=26) and are native to old world cottons. They are also known as Asiatic cottons because they are grown in Asia. The last two species are tetraploid (2n=52) and are also referred to as new world cottons. *G. hirsutum* is also known as American cotton or upland cotton and *G. barbadense* as Egyptian cotton or Sea Island cotton or Peruvian cotton or Tanguish cotton or Quality cotton. *G. hirsutum* is the predominant species which alone contributes about 90% to the global production. Perhaps, India is the only country in the world where all the four cultivated species are grown on commercial scale.

Cotton is one of the most important commercial crops cultivated in India and accounts for around 23% of the total global cotton production. It plays a major role in sustaining the livelihood of an estimated 6 million cotton farmers and 40-50 million people engaged in related activity such as cotton processing & trade. The Indian Textile Industry consumes a diverse range of fibers and yarns and the ratio of use of cotton to non - cotton fibers in India is around 60:40 whereas it is 30:70 in the rest of the world.

As seed is the vital ingredient in modern agriculture, availability of quality seed has remained a major constraint in boosting productivity of cotton. Several factors such as indeterminate fruiting behaviour, galaxy of plant types with variable maturing periods and inappropriate production practices are largely responsible for deterioration in seed quality in cotton. Cotton is also a potential source of edible oil and protein, thus pay important role in Indian economy of agro-industries. The cotton seed cake is used as cattle feed. At present, India is importing edible oil, hence efforts are being made to increase oil production through existing traditional oilseed crops. It is, therefore, absolutely necessary to explore possibilities of exploiting non-traditional edible oilseed crops including cotton seed.

Production and consumption of cotton: India is the only country which grows all four species of cotton *G. arboreum* & *G. herbaceum* (Asian cotton), *G. barbadense* (Egyptian cotton) and *G. hirsutum*

(American/Upland cotton). *G. hirsutum* represents 90% of the hybrid cotton production in India and all the current Bt cotton hybrids are *G. hirsutum*. In India, majority of cotton production comes from 9 major cotton growing states, which are grouped into three diverse agro-ecological zones, as under:- i) Northern Zone - Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan ii) Central Zone - Gujarat, Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh iii) Southern Zone - Telangana, Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka. Apart from the above the cotton is also grown in the state of Odisha and Tamil Nadu. India is having 2nd place in the world with estimated production of 323.11 lakh bales (5.50 Million Metric Tonnes) during cotton season 2023-24 i.e. 23.83% of world cotton production of 1429 lakh bales (24.31 Million Metric Tonnes). India is also the 2nd largest consumer of cotton in the world with estimated consumption of 317 lakh bales (5.39 Million Metric Tonnes i.e. 22.69% of world cotton consumption of 1397 lakh bales (23.75 Million Metric Tonnes) (Anonymous, 2024). National Scenario: Acreage under cotton and yield: India got 1st place in the world in cotton acreage with 124.69 lakh hectares area under cotton cultivation i.e. around 39% of world area of 318.8 lakh hectares. Approximately 67% of Indian's cotton is produced on rain-fed areas and 33% on irrigated lands. In terms of productivity, India is on 33 rd rank with yield of 441 kg/ha (Anonymous, 2024).

Quality seed determines the usefulness of other costlier inputs, like fertilizers, irrigation and agrochemicals. If the quality seed of improved cultivars are not made available to the farmers, the efforts of Plant Breeders will go waste. In cotton crop utilizing high quality seed produce, 18% higher yield can be achieved than those obtained from low quality seed (Bishnoi and Delouche, 1980). Seed quality is of great importance in optimizing the cost of crop establishment. Maintaining the quality of cotton seed at the level as nearly as possible that it is at harvest is of prime concern in producing high quality seed. Measuring seed quality is important in the selection of lots for conditioning and in the quality control program of any seed firm. Eliminating lots not suitable for planting from the market can be invaluable to a seed company as well as to a farmer. It was found that plants from high quality seed produced 18% higher yield than that obtained from low quality seed (Khadi, 2006). With technological advances in the modern agriculture, each seed should readily germinate and produce a vigorous and healthy seedling ensuring maximum yield. Availability of viable and vigorous seeds at planting time is important for achieving targets of agricultural production, because good quality seeds act as a catalyst for realizing the potential of other inputs.

Breeding programmes are determined in the initial step by the variability existing in the base populations. Later, the success of the selected material depends upon the stability of the characters under selection. Thus, understanding the genetic makeup of the crop and the architecture of character set up in that crop are basic to a plant breeder. Genotypic variability is the heritable component of the apparent variability and is expressed as the heritability. Heritability is a result of additive and non-additive effects and is defined as the proportion of phenotypic variability that is due to genotype.

Material And Method

The present investigation was carried out in the Cotton Research Station, Nanded. The experimental material comprised of 20 cotton genotypes collected from various places. The details of the materials are presented in table. These genotypes were sown in the first week of July. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Block Design with three replications with a spacing of 60 cm between the rows and 30 cm between plants within row. Recommended agronomic practices and

need based plant protection measures were adopted. Five plants at random in each replication were chosen and labeled for recording observations. The mean of five plants were used for statistical analysis. The data on the following yield and yield component and quality parameters were recorded. The characters viz., Days to fifty percent flowering, Plant height, Days to maturity, Number of sympodia per plant, Number of monopodia per plant, Number of bolls per plant, Boll weight, Seed cotton yield per plant, Ginning percentage, Upper Half Mean Length, Micronaire value, Tenacity 3.2 mm, Elongation, Test weight, Germination, Seed Vigour Index- I, Seed Vigour Index - II, Seed dry weight, Seed moisture content, Seed Index. Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) and phenotypic co-efficient of variation (PCV) were calculated based on the formula advocated by Burton (1952). Heritability in broad sense was calculated according to Allard (1960) and expressed in percentage. The GA as per cent of mean was classified according to Johnson *et al.* (1955).

Table: List of American cotton genotypes along with their source used in present study

S.N.	Genotype	Source/ Developed at
1.	NH 810	CRS, Nanded
2.	NH 811	CRS, Nanded
3.	NH 812	CRS, Nanded
4.	NH 813	CRS, Nanded
5.	NH 814	CRS, Nanded
6.	NH 815	CRS, Nanded
7.	NH 816	CRS, Nanded
8.	NH 817	CRS, Nanded
9.	NH 818	CRS, Nanded
10.	NH 819	CRS, Nanded
11.	NH 820	CRS, Nanded
12.	NH 821	CRS, Nanded
13.	NH 822	CRS, Nanded
14.	NH 823	CRS, Nanded
15.	NH 824	CRS, Nanded
16.	NH 825	CRS, Nanded
17.	NH 826	CRS, Nanded
18.	NH 677 (Check)	CRS, Nanded
19.	NH 615 (Check)	CRS, Nanded
20.	NH 545 (Check)	CRS, Nanded

Result And Discussion

The analysis of variance revealed significant differences among the accessions for all the characters studied. This indicated that the 20 genotypes differed genetically among themselves for all the characters studied. This implied that there is good scope for further improvement in cotton genotypes. In the present investigation, estimates of genetic parameters revealed that phenotypic coefficient of variability was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variability for all the characters studied which indicated that they are all interacted with the environments to a considerable extent. Similar observations were made by Sakthi *et al.* (2007) and Anjani *et al.* (2020).

In the present study, the traits viz., number of monopodia per plant and seed cotton yield per plant recorded high PCV and GCV, while boll weight, tenacity, micronaire value, number of sympodia per plant, seed vigour index-II, number of bolls per plant, seed vigour index-I showed moderate PCV and GCV. Days to maturity showed low PCV and GCV. There existed a close agreement between PCV and GCV for most of the traits indicating that the observed variation could largely be due to genetic. There was only less influence of environmental effects in general. This reflects on the reliability of the selection based on the phenotypic performance.

The heritability estimates were always high for all the traits of interest. High heritability estimates were observed for Number of monopodia/plant followed by Seed cotton yield per plant, Boll weight and Seed

Vigor Index-II. High genetic advance was observed for Seed Vigor Index-I (412.52) followed by Plant height (cm) (14.83), Seed Vigor Index-II (11.00) and Seed cotton yield/ plant (g) (10.95). whereas, estimated values for genetic advance were least for Seed dry weight (g) (0.08) and EL (%) (0.11) among all other characters indicating the predominance of additive gene action for these traits, enabling case of selection. These findings are in agreement with of Sakthi *et al.* (2007) and Meena *et al.* (2022).

Johnson *et al.* (1955) suggested that heritability estimates in conjunction with the high genetic advance were usually helpful in predicting its resultant effects for selecting the best individuals. High heritability estimates coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean was recorded for most of the traits namely, number of monopodia per plant, seed cotton yield per plant, boll weight and seed vigour index-II. This clearly indicated the existence of additive genetic control in the expression of these traits. This suggested that quick improvement could well be expected in a short time for these characters by following simple pureline selection. High heritability coupled with low to moderate genetic advance as percent of mean was observed for seed vigour index-I, seed index, test weight and germination per cent. This clearly indicated the existence of non-additive gene action in the expression of these traits. This suggested that the improvement cannot be expected by resorting to simple selection procedures for these

characters. These characters could well be exploited by resorting to hybrid breeding.

Reference

1. **Allard, R.W. (1960).** *Principles of Plant Breeding*, John Willey and Sons. Inc. New York, pp. 485.
2. **Anjani, A., Padma, V., Ramana, J.V., and Satish, Y. (2020).** Evaluation of genetic parameters of agro-morpho-quality traits in American cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *Electronic J. Plant Breed.*, 11(1): 279-282.
3. **Anonymous (2024).** Indian Cotton Scenario: 2024-25. As per Committee on Cotton Production and Consumption (COCPC) estimate, Cotton Production in India during 2024-25. Area under cotton cultivation and raw cotton production in the world. pp. 23.
4. **Bishnoi, U.R., and Delouche, J.C. (1980).** Relationship of vigour tests and seed lots to cotton seedling establishment, International Seed Testing Association. *Seed Sci. Technol.*, 8: 341-346.
5. **Burton, G.W. (1952).** Quantitative inheritance in sesame. In: Proc. 6th International Grassland Congress, pp. 177-283.
6. **Johnson, H.W., Robinson, H.F. and Comstock, R.E. (1955)** Estimates of Genetic and Environmental Variability in Soybeans. *Agronomy J.*, 47: 314-318.
7. **Khadi, B.M. (2006).** Impact of Bt cotton on Agriculture in India. In: The World Cotton Research Conference-4 (Sept.10-14), Lubbock, TX.
8. **Meena, R.K., Parmar, L.D., Meena, R.K., Patel, P.R., Tanwar, J., and Joshi, D.P. (2022).** Genetic variability studies of yield and its component traits in upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *The Pharma Innovation J.*, 11(5): 380-384.
9. **Sakthi, A.R., Kumar, M., and Ravikesavan, R. (2007).** Variability and association analysis using morphological and quality traits in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *J. Cotton Res. Dev.*, 21(2): 148-152.
10. **Wallace, T.P., Bowman, D., Campbell, B.T., Chee, P., Gutierrez, O.A., Kohel, R.J., and Weaver, D. (2009).** Status of the USA cotton germplasm collection and crop vulnerability. *Genet. Resources Crop Evol.*, 56: 507-532.

Fig: Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance of yield, yield contributing traits, fiber quality traits and seed quality parameters in cotton genotyp

Table : Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance of yield, yield contributing traits, fiber and seed quality parameters in cotton genotypes

Characters	Range	Mean	Genotypic Variance	Phenotypic Variance	Genotypic Coefficient of Variation	Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation	Heritability(bs)	Genetic Advance	Genetic Advance as % of Mean
Days to 50 % flowering	66-75	72	3.21	14.29	2.49	5.25	22.47	1.75	2.43
Days to maturity	131-145	142	5.86	25.49	1.70	3.55	23.00	2.39	1.68
Plant height (cm)	149.6-203	173.4	112.30	243.43	6.11	8.99	46.15	14.83	8.55
Number of sympodia/ plant	20-30	25	4.27	9.05	8.16	11.88	47.22	2.92	11.56
Number of monopodia/ plant	2-6	4	1.10	1.17	26.27	27.12	93.79	2.09	52.41
Number of bolls/ plant	20-28	25	3.03	8.03	6.98	11.36	37.79	2.20	8.84
Boll weight (g)	1.8-3.5	2.5	0.16	0.19	15.58	17.10	82.95	0.75	29.23
Ginning (%)	34.9-41.6	38.6	1.46	5.92	3.12	6.28	24.69	1.23	3.19
Micronaire value	3.3-4.9	4.1	0.10	0.24	7.92	11.93	44.16	0.45	10.85
UHML	20.4-24.2	22.5	0.65	2.50	3.59	7.01	26.27	0.85	3.79
Tenacity (g/tex)	17.4-24.7	20.1	3.08	6.39	8.69	12.53	48.15	2.50	12.43
EL (%)	5.2-6.0	5.5	0.01	0.05	2.09	4.24	24.35	0.11	2.12
Test weight (g)	55.8-78.2	67.9	24.26	42.45	7.25	9.59	57.15	7.67	11.29
Germination (%)	65.0-85.0	74.6	23.89	45.03	6.55	8.99	53.06	7.33	9.82
Seed Vigor Index-I	2343.4-3317.6	2794.4	63166.70	99497.96	8.99	11.28	63.49	412.52	14.76
Seed Vigor Index-II	55.8-77.6	63.4	39.41	54.40	9.89	11.62	72.44	11.00	17.35
Seed dry weight (g)	0.9-1.2	1.0	0.00	0.01	5.78	8.63	44.80	0.08	7.97
Seed moisture content (%)	10.1-11.4	10.7	0.07	0.33	2.53	5.34	22.57	0.26	2.48
Seed Index	5.6-7.9	6.7	0.26	0.43	7.58	9.80	59.75	0.81	12.07
Seed cotton yield/ plant (g)	11.9-32.4	22.7	30.88	33.70	24.47	25.57	91.62	10.95	48.26